

Case Report: VACTERL Association in a Preterm Newborn with Multisystem AnomaliesSehajdeep Singh Randhawa¹, Ankush Khanna², Dhaarna Mutreja³, Akshita Singla⁴^{1,2}Resident DM Neonatology, Mahatma Gandhi Hospital Jaipur³MS Obstetrics and Gynaecology, MRCOG, Consultant Soni Hospital, Jaipur⁴MD Anaesthesia, Assistant Professor, Mahatma Gandhi Hospital Jaipur

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** VACTERL association is a rare and complex congenital disorder characterized by the presence of anomalies in at least three organ systems.**Case Report:** A male neonate, delivered at 35 weeks of gestation via elective lower segment Cesarean section (LSCS) due to severe maternal polyhydramnios, presented with multiple congenital anomalies shortly after birth. The constellation of these anomalies led to the diagnosis of VACTERL association. A multidisciplinary neonatal care team, post-operative course was complicated by a transient period of neonatal sepsis, successfully treated with broad-spectrum antibiotics. Finally the patient was discharged.**Keywords:** VACTERL, congenital disorder, anomalies.

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Introduction

VACTERL association is a rare and complex congenital disorder characterized by the presence of anomalies in at least three organ systems from the following: vertebral anomalies, anal atresia, cardiac defects, tracheoesophageal fistula, esophageal atresia, renal anomalies, and limb abnormalities. The incidence of VACTERL association is estimated at 1 in 10,000 to 1 in 40,000 live births, making it a rare but critical diagnosis in neonatology [1].

The pathogenesis is believed to involve a combination of genetic and environmental factors during embryogenesis, particularly during the critical period of organ development between the third and seventh weeks of gestation [2]. Recent advancements in genetic research and prenatal diagnostics have provided new insights into the etiology, diagnosis, and management of VACTERL association, contributing to improved outcomes for affected infants [3].

Case Presentation

A male neonate, delivered at 35 weeks of gestation via elective lower segment cesarean section (LSCS) due to severe maternal polyhydramnios, presented with multiple congenital anomalies shortly after birth. The infant, born to a non-consanguineous couple, was the first child, and the pregnancy was complicated by polyhydramnios, often associated with gastrointestinal obstructions like esophageal

atresia [4]. At birth, the neonate exhibited significant respiratory distress, characterized by tachypnea, excessive drooling, and recurrent episodes of bilious vomiting. Physical examination revealed a spectrum of congenital anomalies, including:

- Imperforate anus: Absence of an anal opening, necessitating urgent surgical intervention [5].
- Congenital Talipes Equinovarus (CTEV): Bilateral clubfoot, requiring orthopedic management [6].
- Right renal agenesis: Confirmed via ultrasound, indicating the absence of the right kidney, with compensatory hypertrophy of the left kidney [7].
- Esophageal atresia with tracheoesophageal fistula (TEF): Diagnosed by the inability to pass a nasogastric tube beyond the third thoracic vertebra (T3), corroborated by a chest radiograph showing the tube coiled at this level [8].

The constellation of these anomalies led to the diagnosis of VACTERL association. A multidisciplinary neonatal care team, including neonatologists, pediatric surgeons, cardiologists, and orthopedic specialists, was assembled to address the complex needs of the infant. The initial surgical interventions included the primary repair of esophageal atresia and TEF, and a colostomy was performed to manage the imperforate anus.

Orthopedic management for CTEV was initiated with serial casting, with plans for potential future surgical correction.

The infant's post-operative course was complicated by a transient period of neonatal sepsis, successfully treated with broad-spectrum antibiotics. Prolonged respiratory support and parenteral nutrition were required until safe enteral feeding could be established via a gastrostomy tube. The infant was discharged after a prolonged stay in the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), with a comprehensive plan for ongoing multidisciplinary follow-up to monitor renal function, bowel management, and orthopedic outcomes.

Pathogenesis and Genetic Considerations: The pathogenesis of VACTERL association involves disruptions during the embryonic development period, particularly between the third and seventh weeks of gestation. These disruptions may be due to a combination of genetic mutations, teratogenic exposures, or other environmental factors [3]. Recent genetic studies have suggested a potential role for the Sonic Hedgehog (SHH) signaling pathway, which is critical for the development of multiple organ systems, including the vertebrae, trachea, and limbs [4]. Mutations in this pathway, along with other genetic factors such as *FOXF1*, *HOXD13*, and *ZIC3*, have been implicated in the etiology of VACTERL association, although no single gene mutation has been consistently identified across all cases [5].

Recent advancements in genetic testing, such as whole-exome sequencing (WES) and chromosomal microarray analysis (CMA), have enabled the identification of rare de novo mutations and copy number variations (CNVs) that may contribute to the development of VACTERL association. These technologies have provided new insights into the genetic underpinnings of the disorder, although the majority of cases remain idiopathic, with no identifiable genetic cause [6].

Latest Developments in Diagnosis and Management

Advancements in Prenatal Diagnosis: The early detection of VACTERL association has been significantly enhanced by advancements in prenatal imaging techniques. High-resolution fetal ultrasound and fetal MRI have become critical tools in the early detection of congenital anomalies associated with VACTERL [7]. These imaging modalities allow for the detailed assessment of fetal anatomy, enabling the identification of characteristic features such as vertebral defects, renal agenesis, and gastrointestinal obstructions. Additionally, the use of three-dimensional (3D) ultrasound has improved the visualization of fetal

structures, aiding in the early diagnosis and management planning.

Furthermore, non-invasive prenatal testing (NIPT) has emerged as a valuable tool for the early detection of chromosomal abnormalities that may be associated with VACTERL association. While NIPT primarily screens for common trisomies, its use in detecting other chromosomal abnormalities and CNVs is expanding, providing valuable information for the prenatal diagnosis of complex congenital syndromes [3].

Improvements in Surgical Techniques and Postoperative Care: The surgical management of VACTERL association has also benefited from advancements in minimally invasive surgical techniques. Laparoscopic and thoracoscopic approaches have increasingly replaced traditional open surgeries for the correction of anomalies such as esophageal atresia and TEF (8). These minimally invasive techniques are associated with reduced postoperative pain, shorter recovery times, and improved cosmetic outcomes. Additionally, advances in neonatal anesthesia and perioperative care have contributed to improved survival rates and reduced morbidity in infants undergoing complex surgical procedures.

Postoperative care has also seen significant advancements, particularly in the management of respiratory and nutritional challenges in infants with VACTERL association. The use of advanced ventilatory support techniques, including high-frequency oscillatory ventilation (HFOV) and extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO), has improved outcomes for infants with severe respiratory compromise [6]. Moreover, the implementation of standardized feeding protocols and the use of specialized formulas have addressed the nutritional challenges associated with esophageal atresia and TEF, promoting better growth and development in affected infants.

Genetic Counselling and Long-Term Follow-Up: Given the multifactorial nature of VACTERL association, genetic counselling is an essential component of care for affected families. Recent developments in genetic testing have enabled more accurate risk assessment and recurrence prediction, allowing for personalized counseling and family planning [4]. Long-term follow-up is critical for monitoring the ongoing medical and developmental needs of children with VACTERL association. This includes regular assessments of renal function, growth, and developmental milestones, as well as monitoring for potential complications such as scoliosis, recurrent infections, and gastrointestinal issues [7].

Discussion

The management of VACTERL association requires a highly coordinated, multidisciplinary

approach due to the involvement of multiple organ systems and the need for complex surgical and medical interventions [1]. Early diagnosis, often facilitated by prenatal imaging, is critical for planning appropriate postnatal management. The integration of advanced genetic testing and prenatal imaging has revolutionized the diagnostic approach to VACTERL association, allowing for earlier intervention and improved outcomes [8]. The long-term prognosis for children with VACTERL association varies widely, depending on the severity and combination of defects present. In this case, the neonate's prognosis is cautiously optimistic, given the successful surgical interventions and the absence of severe cardiac anomalies. However, the child will require ongoing medical care, including regular monitoring for renal function, bowel management following colostomy, and orthopedic care for CTEV. The potential for developmental delays and other long-term complications underscores the need for comprehensive, multidisciplinary follow-up.

Similar Cases Worldwide: Several cases of VACTERL association have been reported worldwide, each highlighting the variability and complexity of this disorder. Solomon et al. documented a series of patients with VACTERL association, noting the frequent co-occurrence of vertebral anomalies, anal atresia, and cardiac defects, and emphasizing the importance of early recognition and a multidisciplinary approach to management [1].

A particularly challenging case reported by Rittler et al. involved a neonate with VACTERL association who presented with severe vertebral anomalies, esophageal atresia, and renal agenesis [2]. The complexity of managing such cases is heightened by the need for coordinated care across multiple specialties, particularly in resource-limited settings where access to specialized care may be restricted. These cases highlight the importance of early diagnosis and the role of multidisciplinary teams in optimizing outcomes for affected infants.

Additionally, a study by Bermejo-Sánchez et al. analyzed the epidemiology of VACTERL association across Europe, using data from the EUROCAT registry. The study reported significant variability in the incidence and outcomes of VACTERL association, depending on the specific combination of anomalies present [9]. This variability further underscores the need for personalized treatment plans and long-term follow-up for affected patients.

Conclusion

VACTERL association is a rare and complex congenital disorder that poses significant diagnostic

and management challenges. The integration of advanced genetic testing and prenatal imaging has significantly improved the early detection and management of VACTERL association. This case underscores the importance of a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach to care, involving early diagnosis, timely surgical interventions, and coordinated long-term follow-up. While significant progress has been made in understanding and managing this disorder, further research is needed to elucidate the underlying genetic and environmental factors contributing to its development. Continued documentation and study of rare cases worldwide will enhance our understanding of this condition and ultimately lead to improved care and outcomes for affected individuals.

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